

1 **Neurotransmission in triple negative breast cancer.**

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6 Neurotransmission in the primary tumor was similar to that found in hormone receptor positive breast
7 cancer but was characterized by high expression of adrenomedullin 2 (ADM2), enrichment of
8 neuropeptide machinery including neuropeptide S receptor *NPSR1*, neuropeptides B and W receptor
9 *NPBWR1*, neuropeptide Y receptor type 4 *NPY4R*, peptide *YY2* and the hypocretin precursor peptide
10 *HCRT*. Other specific features of the TNBC neurotransmission system was expression of melanocyte
11 neuronal machinery including melanocortin 2 receptor (*MC2R*), and expression of the nerve growth factor
12 *VEGF* rather than traditional neurotrophic factors *MANF*, *NDNF* and *CNTF*.